

Law on Carbon Credit Trading on the Voluntary Carbon Market

Tran Van Mong

Thu Dau Mot University

ABSTRACT: This article analyzes the legal framework governing carbon credit trading on the Voluntary Carbon Market (VCM) in Vietnam in the context of achieving a net zero emission commitment by 2050. Based on a survey of Party documents, the current legal framework (Environmental Protection Law 2020, Decree 06/2022/ND-CP, Decree 119/2025/ND-CP, Decision 232/QD-TTg 2025), and a comparison with international standards (Kyoto Protocol, Paris Agreement), Based on the VCS (Gold Standard) standards, this article points out shortcomings in the legal definition, ownership rights, measurement-reporting-verification (MRV) mechanism, taxation, accounting, and dispute resolution for voluntary carbon credits. Based on this, the author proposes directions for improving the law to ensure that the voluntary carbon market in Vietnam operates transparently, harmonizes the interests of stakeholders, and is interconnected with regional and global markets.

KEYWORDS: carbon credits; voluntary carbon market; Net Zero; Decree 06/2022/ND-CP; carbon credit ownership rights.

1. INTRODUCTION

Climate change has become one of the greatest non-traditional security challenges of the 21st century. At the 26th Conference of the Parties to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (COP26) held in Glasgow in 2021, Vietnam announced its goal of achieving net-zero emissions by 2050, demonstrating the nation's highest political determination in responding to climate change. This commitment is based on the strategic directions of the Party. The Resolution of the 13th National Congress of the Communist Party of Vietnam identified the task of “proactively and effectively adapting to climate change, preventing, combating and mitigating natural disasters and epidemics, managing, exploiting, and using resources rationally, economically, efficiently and sustainably; taking the protection of the living environment and people's health as the top priority... building a green economy, a circular economy, and an environmentally friendly economy” (Central Committee of the Communist Party of Vietnam, 2021). This spirit continues to be inherited and developed in the Documents of the 14th National Congress, in which environmental protection, effective adaptation to climate change, and building institutions to promote the development of a green economy and a circular economy linked to socio-economic development are elevated to a central task, marking the Party's profound understanding of sustainable development based on the three pillars of Economy - Society - Environment (Central Committee of the Communist Party of Vietnam, 2025).

To realize these commitments, carbon pricing tools, especially carbon markets, are identified as key economic mechanisms. Within the global carbon market structure, voluntary carbon markets play a crucial complementary role to compliance markets, enabling businesses, organizations, and individuals to proactively participate in emission offsetting, and promoting investment in emission reduction and greenhouse gas absorption projects. However, in Vietnam, the legal framework regulating carbon credit trading in voluntary markets is still under development, with many gaps and overlaps. Researching and clarifying the legal issues related to carbon credit trading in voluntary markets is not only of scientific significance but also has urgent practical value, directly contributing to the improvement of the socialist-oriented market economy and the implementation of the country's sustainable development strategy.

2. THEORETICAL BASIS OF CARBON CREDITS AND VOLUNTARY CARBON MARKETS

2.1. Concept of Carbon Credits and Voluntary Carbon Credits

The concept of carbon credits originated from the Kyoto Protocol of 1997 (UNFCCC, 1997). According to this protocol, countries with excess emission rights can sell or purchase them from countries that emit more or less than their committed targets. From this, a new type of commodity emerged worldwide: certificates for reducing/absorbing greenhouse gas emissions. Because carbon is the equivalent of all greenhouse gases, these transactions are collectively called carbon trading, forming a carbon market or carbon credit market.

In Vietnam, the concept of carbon credits was first legalized in the 2020 Environmental Protection Law. According to the 2020 Environmental Protection Law, a carbon credit is a commercially tradable certificate representing the right to emit one ton of CO₂ or one ton of CO₂ equivalent (National Assembly, 2020). Specific technical regulations are outlined in Decree 06/2022/ND-CP, in which 1 unit of greenhouse gas emission quota equals 1 ton of CO₂ equivalent; carbon credits obtained from programs and projects under the carbon credit exchange mechanism are

Law on Carbon Credit Trading on the Voluntary Carbon Market

allowed to be converted into offsetting units for greenhouse gas emission quotas on the exchange; 1 carbon credit equals 1 ton of CO₂ equivalent (Government, 2022a).

2.2. Distinguishing between Voluntary and Mandatory Carbon Markets

Carbon markets are divided into two basic types. Compliance carbon markets are established through the obligations of countries that have signed and ratified the Kyoto Protocol, so projects under the KP mechanisms are considered mandatory carbon markets (VTN & Partners, 2023). Voluntary carbon markets are based on bilateral or multilateral agreements between organizations, companies, or countries.

The essential characteristic of a voluntary market is its non-coercive nature in terms of government participation. Voluntary markets include all carbon offsetting transactions not purchased with the intention of serving a mandatory carbon market (Ecosystem Marketplace, 2024). This market includes carbon offsetting quantities purchased for the purpose of resale or suspension to meet carbon neutrality or other environmental claims. Voluntary carbon offsetting is driven by companies and individuals responsible for offsetting their own emissions, known as fully voluntary buyers, as well as entities that purchase mandatory cash carbon offsetting before emission reductions are required by regulations.

The distinction between these two types of markets has significant legal implications. Compliance markets operate primarily on a "cap-and-trade" mechanism where the State allocates quotas and imposes compliance obligations; whereas voluntary markets are private environmental finance markets, operating primarily based on contracts between parties, international certification organization standards, and legal regulations on trade, investment, and taxation.

2.3. Characteristics and Scale of the Global Voluntary Carbon Market

The voluntary carbon market has undergone significant changes in recent years. At its peak, this market was valued at approximately \$2 billion, a small fraction of what is needed to achieve global climate goals (Ecosystem Marketplace, 2024). After peaking in 2021, the value of VCMs fell to \$723 million in 2023, and the volume of credits more than halved from 253.8 MtCO₂e in 2022. On average in 2023, buyers paid \$6.53 per ton of carbon credits, a slight decrease from 2022 (Ecosystem Marketplace, 2025). The average price of carbon credits in 2023 remained higher than any year prior to 2022. According to market research organizations, the global voluntary carbon credit market is estimated to reach US\$4.04 billion in 2024 and is projected to reach US\$23.99 billion by 2030, growing at a CAGR of 35.1% between 2025 and 2030 (Grand View Research, 2025).

A key trend is the shift towards higher quality standards. Initiatives such as the Integrity Council for Voluntary Carbon Markets (ICVCM) are responding to concerns by raising quality standards for VCMs (Ecosystem Marketplace, 2024). ICVCM's core Carbon principles aim to guide markets toward more consistent and higher-quality standards, ensuring that trading credits are truly complementary, long-lasting, quantifiable, transparent, and traceable.

3. INTERNATIONAL LEGAL FRAMEWORK FOR VOLUNTARY CARBON CREDIT TRANSACTIONS

3.1. Foundational International Treaties

The international legal framework for carbon credit transactions is built on the foundation of three main documents: the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) of 1992, the Kyoto Protocol of 1997, and the Paris Agreement of 2015.

The Clean Development Mechanism (CDM) under Article 12 of the Kyoto Protocol is an important precursor to carbon credit activities in developing countries. This mechanism allows parties to receive credits in the form of "certified emission reductions," abbreviated as CER (1 CER = 1 ton of CO₂ equivalent) (UNFCCC, 1997). Following the entry into force of the Paris Agreement, Article 6 established a new cooperation mechanism, including Article 6.2 on the transfer of emission reduction results with national consent (Internationally Transferred Mitigation Outcomes - ITMOs) and Article 6.4 on the sustainable development mechanism (UNFCCC, 2015).

3.2. International Voluntary Carbon Credit Standards

In the voluntary market, certification standards play the role of "soft law" that effectively governs the quality of carbon credits. Popular standards include the Verified Carbon Standard (VCS) administered by Verra, Gold Standard (GS), American Carbon Registry (ACR), Climate Action Reserve (CAR), Plan Vivo, and Global Carbon Council (GCC). Each standard has its own methodology, independent validation process, and mechanism for registering and revoking credits.

3.3. Legal Experiences of Several Countries

The European Union operates the EU Emissions Trading System (ETS) – the world's largest compliant carbon market – and has established the Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM), which indirectly pressures exporting countries, including Vietnam. South Korea, Japan (with the Joint Crediting Mechanism - JCM), Singapore, China, etc., have all enacted specific laws on carbon markets. In the ASEAN region, recent additions include Indonesia's carbon trading program launched in late 2023, Vietnam's pilot program starting in 2024, and Malaysia's emissions trading system expected in early 2025; together, these markets cover approximately 23% of global greenhouse gas emissions (International Carbon Action Partnership, 2025).

Law on Carbon Credit Trading on the Voluntary Carbon Market

4. VIETNAMESE LEGAL FRAMEWORK ON VOLUNTARY CARBON CREDIT TRADING

4.1. Policy Orientations of the Party and State

The orientation for developing the carbon market in Vietnam is formed on the consistent basis of the Party's viewpoints. Resolution No. 24-NQ/TW dated June 3, 2013, of the 11th Central Committee of the Communist Party of Vietnam on proactively responding to climate change, strengthening resource management and environmental protection is the foundational document (Central Committee of the Communist Party of Vietnam, 2013). Subsequently, the Politburo issued Conclusion No. 56-KL/TW dated August 23, 2019 (Politburo, 2019) and Conclusion No. 81-KL/TW dated June 4, 2024, continuing to implement Resolution No. 7 of the 11th Central Committee (Politburo, 2024). The Resolution of the 13th National Congress of the Communist Party of Vietnam requires proactive and effective response to climate change, development of a green economy, a low-carbon economy, and mitigation of greenhouse gas emissions (Central Committee of the Communist Party of Vietnam, 2021). In the draft documents for the 14th National Congress, the requirement to protect the environment, effectively adapt to climate change, and build institutions to promote the development of a green economy and a circular economy linked to socio-economic development has been elevated to a central task.

Based on this, the Government has issued the National Climate Change Strategy for the period up to 2050 (Decision No. 896/QĐ-TTg dated July 26, 2022) along with many other strategies, plans, and projects. The overall goal of this Strategy is to proactively and effectively adapt to climate change and achieve the goal of net zero emissions (Prime Minister, 2022b). The updated Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC) in 2022 commits to voluntarily reducing greenhouse gas emissions by 15.8% by 2030 compared to the business-as-usual (BAU) scenario, and potentially by up to 43.5% with international support.

4.2. Current System Of Legal Documents

4.2.1. Environmental Protection Law 2020

The Environmental Protection Law 2020 is the highest legal foundation for Vietnam's carbon market, especially in Articles 91 (greenhouse gas emission reduction), 92 (ozone layer protection), and 139 (organization and development of the carbon market). With the enactment of the Environmental Protection Law 2020, Vietnam has established strict regulations on the protection and development of natural resources, especially forests, with the goal of absorbing and storing carbon (National Assembly, 2020). This law not only clearly defines the responsibility for forest conservation but also emphasizes the important role of forests in mitigating and responding to climate change. The regulations in the law have created a strong legal foundation to promote forest carbon credit activities.

4.2.2. Decree 06/2022/ND-CP - the central document

On January 7, 2022, the Government issued Decree No. 06/2022/ND-CP regulating greenhouse gas emission reduction and ozone layer protection. This is considered the first legal document demonstrating the strong commitment of the Vietnamese Government in contributing to the fight against global climate change (VTN & Partners, 2023). This Decree details several articles of the Law on Environmental Protection, including Article 91 on greenhouse gas emission reduction, Article 92 on ozone layer protection, and Article 139 on the organization and development of the carbon market (Government, 2022a). Specifically, the Decree stipulates the development roadmap and the timing of the implementation of the domestic carbon market.

Regarding transaction principles, Article 3 of Decree 06 establishes the fundamental principles. The exchange of greenhouse gas emission quotas and carbon credits ensures transparency and harmonizes the interests of all entities in the carbon market (Government, 2022a). Organizations and individuals participate in the carbon market on a voluntary basis. This is a particularly important principle because it acknowledges the contractual and voluntary nature of market participation, although for entities required to inventory greenhouse gases, "voluntariness" here only applies to carbon credits, not to mandatory quotas.

Regarding participants, according to Article 16 of Decree 06/2022/ND-CP: Establishments falling under the scope of Clause 1, Article 5 of this Decree; Organizations participating in the exchange and offsetting of carbon credits domestically and internationally in accordance with the provisions of law and international treaties to which the Socialist Republic of Vietnam is a signatory; Other organizations and individuals involved in investment and business activities related to greenhouse gas emission quotas and carbon credits on the carbon market (Government, 2022a).

Regarding the authority to certify carbon credits on the domestic exchange, Article 19 of Decree 06 stipulates that the Ministry of Natural Resources and Environment certifies carbon credits and greenhouse gas emission quotas traded on the exchange, including: The amount of carbon credits obtained from programs and projects under the domestic and international carbon credit exchange and offsetting mechanism in accordance with the provisions of law and international treaties to which the Socialist Republic of Vietnam is a member; Greenhouse gas emission quotas allocated as stipulated in Clause 2, Article 12 of this Decree (Government, 2022a).

Regarding the development roadmap, Article 17 of Decree 06 has designed two clear phases. The phase until the end of 2027 focuses on institutional building and pilot operation; The exchange will officially be operational from 2028 onwards (Government, 2022a).

4.2.3. Decree 119/2025/ND-CP and Decision 232/QĐ-TTg

To update the legal framework to suit practical realities, on June 9, 2025, the Government issued Decree 119/2025/ND-CP (effective from August 1, 2025), amending and supplementing Decree 06/2022/ND-CP (Government, 2025). The new Decree adds many implementing regulations, notably the decentralization of authority for assessment, the roadmap for allocating emission quotas to large-scale emitters, and

Law on Carbon Credit Trading on the Voluntary Carbon Market

specific regulations on registration, declaration, transfer, and offsetting of credits and quotas on the National Carbon Exchange, connected to the centralized electronic registration system.

Simultaneously, on January 24, 2025, the Prime Minister of Vietnam issued Decision No. 232/QĐ-TTg ("Decision 232"), approving the plan for establishing and developing the country's carbon market. Decision 232 primarily aims to establish a carbon market in Vietnam to support the implementation of greenhouse gas emission reduction targets outlined in the Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC), while minimizing costs for businesses and society (Prime Minister, 2025). This plan will promote new financial support for Vietnam's greenhouse gas reduction efforts, promote the transition to green technologies, and enhance the competitiveness of local businesses in both domestic and international markets.

Decision 232 clearly categorizes two carbon market commodities. The Vietnamese carbon market will introduce two main products: Greenhouse gas emission quotas and Certified Carbon Credits. Emission quotas, operating similarly to a cap-and-trade system, will be issued by the Government through allocation or auction (Vietnam Law Magazine, 2025). Businesses exceeding emission limits can purchase quotas through the carbon market, while businesses under-emission can sell the surplus. This approach is consistent with a mandatory carbon market. Certified Carbon Credits will operate similarly to a voluntary carbon market. Businesses can obtain carbon credits through international emission reduction programs such as the Clean Development Mechanism (CDM), the Joint Crediting Mechanism (JCM), or the Article 6 mechanism of the Paris Agreement.

4.3. Vietnam's Practice in Participating in the Voluntary Carbon Market

Vietnam has a history of participating in the voluntary carbon market for more than two decades. Over the past 20 years, Vietnam has actively participated in the voluntary carbon market. According to data published by the UNFCCC, as of September 2023, there were 258 Clean Development Mechanism (CDM) projects and 15 working groups registered, with over 32 million emission reduction certificates issued (International Carbon Action Partnership, 2025). This makes Vietnam one of the four countries with the most registered CDM projects, after China, Brazil, and India.

In addition to CDM, Vietnam has developed other carbon initiatives in line with various international standards. According to data published on the Voluntary Registry Offsets database at the Goldman School of Public Policy, as of May 2023, Vietnam had 70 projects registered under the GOLD standard and 52 projects registered under the VCS standard, with a total of over 7 million and 2 million credits issued respectively (International Carbon Action Partnership, 2025). According to the Global Environment Centre Foundation, as of May 2023, Vietnam also had 44 initiatives related to the Joint Crediting Mechanism, with over 3,100 carbon credits issued. In addition, according to the Ministry of Industry and Trade's website, nearly 50 projects issuing carbon credits under the Global Carbon Council mechanism have been submitted. There are four crediting mechanisms: the Clean Development Mechanism (CDM), the Joint Crediting Mechanism (JCM), the Gold Standard (GS), and the Certified Carbon Scheme (GCS). The total number of credits issued in Vietnam up to December 2022 was over 40 million credits (National Assembly, 2020).

A notable achievement is the transaction of forest carbon credits in the North Central region. In March 2024, Vietnam received a payment of US\$51.5 million for verified emission reductions, known as carbon credits, for efforts to reduce deforestation and forest degradation through REDD+ and increase carbon sequestration through reforestation and afforestation (World Bank, 2024). This achievement makes Vietnam the first country in the East Asia-Pacific region to receive a results-based payment from the World Bank's Forest Carbon Partnership Fund (FCPF). The payment was awarded to Vietnam for reducing 10.3 million tonnes of carbon emissions from February 1, 2018, to December 31, 2019. This is the largest single payment ever made by the FCPF for verified and high-integrity carbon credits.

Regarding the potential supply forecast, it is projected that in the future, Vietnam will have approximately 10.8 million voluntary carbon credits supplied annually, accompanied by a large demand for exchange and trading (National Assembly, 2020). However, the price is still quite low. Currently, the price of carbon on the voluntary market worldwide usually fluctuates from 2 to 4 USD/ton of carbon, with the average price of carbon from programs/projects in the Asian region fluctuating over the years 2019, 2020, and 2021 being 1.8; 1.6; and 3.09 USD/ton of carbon respectively (VTN & Partners, 2023). The current average price of this market is 1.07 USD/ton of carbon.

5. LIMITATIONS AND SHORTCOMINGS IN VIETNAMESE LAW ON VOLUNTARY CARBON CREDIT TRANSACTIONS

5.1. The Gap in the Legal Definition and Nature of Carbon Credits

Although the 2020 Environmental Protection Law introduced the concept of carbon credits, this definition is still too general and insufficient to fully establish their legal nature. Some experts note that without a clear definition of carbon credits, the market is likely to fall into chaos, causing businesses to be confused in transactions, mortgages, or dispute resolution (Government, 2025).

The core legal question that has not been fully answered is: are carbon credits assets in the sense of the 2015 Civil Code or a specific type of property right? Is it ownership, property right, or a form of "security"? The lack of clear definition of their legal nature leads to many consequences in determining tax regimes, accounting, measures to secure the fulfillment of obligations (pledging, mortgaging), inheritance, and dispute resolution.

Law on Carbon Credit Trading on the Voluntary Carbon Market

5.2. The Issue of Carbon Credit Ownership, Especially Forest Carbon Credits

This is one of the biggest bottlenecks currently. The necessary legal framework (in the Civil Code and related laws) must include specific regulations on ownership rights over carbon credits (VTN & Partners, 2023). Establishing carbon credit ownership rights must simultaneously achieve a dual objective: minimizing disputes between forest owners or project owners when implementing renewable energy investment projects, while also encouraging organizations and individuals to participate in investing in and exploiting carbon credits.

The practical experience from Quang Nam has clearly shown this difficulty. Obstacles from the Forest Carbon Credit Sale Project in Quang Nam show that the bottleneck lies in the lack of regulations in legal documents, leading to the fact that state management activities on forest carbon such as investigation, statistics, inventory, monitoring of changes and annual forest supervision have not been published (VTN & Partners, 2023). Therefore, without a legal framework to regulate and ensure that relevant state agencies have the obligation to coordinate, it is very difficult for localities to design and successfully implement carbon credits on their own.

5.3. Incomplete Measurement - Reporting - Verification (MRV) System

The MRV (Measurement - Reporting - Verification) system is the technical backbone of any carbon market. Decree 06 sets out rules for the national measurement, reporting and verification system on greenhouse gas emission reduction, along with rules on greenhouse gas inventory (International Carbon Action Partnership, 2025). However, these regulations remain at the framework level. Vietnam does not yet have a sufficiently strong, internationally recognized independent audit organization (DOE), leading to the risk of "junk credits"—credits that do not guarantee complementarity, longevity, or quantification. Dr. Nguyen Thi Quynh Anh warned of the risk of "junk credits" if independent oversight is lacking, while Mr. Tran Anh Tuan (Institute of International Economics and Law) also expressed concern that a weak legal framework could make the carbon market merely a formality, lacking real effectiveness (Government, 2025).

5.4. The legal effectiveness of the current legal framework is still low.

Regulations on carbon credits are currently only at the decree and decision level. Decree 119/2025 is a strong shift from "having regulations" to "having enforcement capacity" (Government, 2025). However, both current decrees are still only regulations below the level of law, insufficient to form a comprehensive legal framework that ensures the carbon market operates effectively. "It is impossible to manage a market worth hundreds of millions of USD annually with only decrees below the level of law. We need a law that clarifies the ownership, trading, pricing, and supervision of carbon credits, the trading process, pricing, and supervision mechanism, similar to how the Securities Law laid the foundation for the financial market before" (Government, 2025).

5.5. Lack of Regulations on Taxation, Accounting, Contracts, and Disputes

The handling of taxes on income from the transfer of carbon credits (corporate income tax, value-added tax on cross-border activities) lacks specific guidance. Vietnamese Accounting Standards (VAS) do not yet define what type of asset carbon credits are recognized as. Laws on contracts for the purchase and sale of carbon credits, especially contracts with foreign elements (Emission Reduction Purchase Agreements - ERPAs), have not been codified. Mechanisms for resolving disputes – particularly disputes concerning complementarity, disputes between forest owners and project developers, and cross-border disputes – lack specific regulations.

5.6. Business Capacity and Delays

Initial preparations planned for 2025 have extended into 2026. Recent analyses show that Vietnam is now aiming to launch its carbon trading platform by the end of 2026, about a year behind schedule (International Carbon Action Partnership, 2025). Full mandatory implementation (with all operational systems and expanded scope) is still expected in 2029, but the pilot trading phase may actually last from 2026-2028.

6. ORIENTATIONS AND SOLUTIONS FOR IMPROVING THE LEGAL FRAMEWORK FOR CARBON CREDIT TRADING IN VOLUNTARY MARKETS

6.1. Early Development and Promulgation of the Carbon Market Law

This is a fundamental recommendation. Vietnam should soon promulgate a comprehensive, synchronized, and internationally integrated Carbon Market Law (Government, 2025). A framework law on carbon markets should include core elements such as a clear legal definition of carbon credits, emission quotas, carbon commodities, and emission ownership to ensure a trading basis and legal protection; establishing processes for the allocation, verification, trading, transfer, and accounting of carbon credits according to international standards, ensuring no duplication and connectivity with regional and global markets; a transparent mechanism for allocating and auctioning emission quotas, combining free allocation for essential industries and public auctions for the commercial sector, learning from the experiences of the EU ETS or South Korea; standardizing the MRV system with national standards and independent auditing; and a robust enforcement framework against fraud, deception, and falsification of carbon credits, as well as a clear mechanism for resolving complaints and disputes

6.2. Improving the legal framework for ownership and property rights regarding carbon credits

The 2015 Civil Code needs to be amended or supplemented, or a specialized law should be enacted to clearly define carbon credits as a type of intangible asset – a special property right. For forest carbon credits, regulations are needed to clearly define the entities entitled to benefits corresponding to the form of forest ownership (natural forest, planted forest, production forest, protection forest, special-use forest) and their

Law on Carbon Credit Trading on the Voluntary Carbon Market

relationship with the state-owned forest management agency. Simultaneously, there must be regulations for the fair distribution of benefits between the State, the community, households, and businesses participating in the project.

6.3. Improving the Legal Framework for Carbon Credit Sales Contracts

A model carbon credit sales contract (especially ERPA) should be developed that conforms to international practices but is compatible with Vietnamese law. It should clearly define the applicable law, the dispute resolution body (international commercial arbitration or Vietnamese courts), the conditions for transferring carbon credits abroad (especially credits related to NDCs and the Article 6 mechanism of the Paris Agreement), and the principle of avoiding double counting. For internationally transferred credits, a suitable Letter of Authorization (LoA) mechanism should be established.

6.4. Strengthening the MRV System and Independent Verification Organizations

National standards for MRV should be issued for each type of project (forests, renewable energy, agriculture, waste treatment). Domestic organizations should be encouraged to be recognized as Designated Operational Entities (DOEs). 6.4. Building a national registry system integrated with blockchain technology to ensure transparency, traceability, and fraud prevention. The Ministry of Natural Resources and Environment will issue regulations allowing, supervising, and managing the national registry system and the MRV system, while the Hanoi Stock Exchange (HNX) will operate a carbon exchange (International Carbon Action Partnership, 2025).

6.5. Completing regulations on tax and accounting for carbon credit transactions

A joint circular or guidance document from the Ministry of Finance is needed on the tax regime (corporate income tax, value-added tax, tax incentives for emission reduction projects) and accounting standards for carbon credits. Reference can be made to IFRIC 3 - Emission Rights and drafts of the IFRS Foundation on carbon credit accounting.

6.6. Developing a Synchronized Green Financial Ecosystem

Following the direction affirmed in Party documents, it is necessary to gradually form and perfect the policy framework for green financial products such as green bonds, green credit, green investment funds, environmental insurance, and financial mechanisms supporting adaptation to climate change (Central Committee of the Communist Party of Vietnam, 2021). The development of green finance not only aims to meet the capital needs for environmental projects, but also plays a role in redirecting capital flows in the economy, encouraging environmentally friendly production and business activities, while gradually limiting activities that cause high pollution and emissions.

6.7. Strengthening the Capacity of Businesses, Especially SMEs

It is necessary to raise awareness and capacity for businesses, especially small and medium-sized enterprises, to ensure their effective participation in the market (Vietnam Law Magazine, 2025). Vietnam should study connecting the domestic market with the international market to optimize the benefits from carbon credit trading. At the same time, ministries and agencies need to implement training programs and provide technical support on greenhouse gas inventory and develop emission reduction projects according to international standards (VCS, GS) for businesses.

6.8. Proactively Integrating with Regional and Global Carbon Markets

Vietnam needs to accelerate negotiations on bilateral agreements under Article 6.2 of the Paris Agreement (already signed with Singapore, South Korea, and Japan on JCM). At the same time, it is necessary to prepare well for dealing with the EU's CBAM, expected to be fully implemented from 2026, which will directly impact key export sectors such as iron and steel, cement, aluminum, fertilizers, electricity, and hydrogen.

7. CONCLUSION

The legal framework for carbon credit trading on the voluntary carbon market in Vietnam is entering a period of strong development, reflecting the high political determination of the Party and State in fulfilling the Net Zero commitment by 2050, as well as the policy of developing a green economy and circular economy in the spirit of the 13th National Congress and being inherited and elevated in the Draft Document of the 14th National Congress. With the promulgation of the 2020 Environmental Protection Law, Decree 06/2022/ND-CP, Decree 119/2025/ND-CP, and Decision 232/QĐ-TTg, Vietnam has gradually established a basic legal framework, creating a foundation for the pilot operation of a carbon credit exchange and the official operation of a full carbon market in the 2028-2029 period.

However, the current legal system still has many gaps, especially in defining the legal nature of carbon credits, ownership rights, the MRV system, tax regime, accounting, contracts, and dispute resolution. To ensure that the voluntary carbon market operates effectively, transparently, harmonizes interests, and is interconnected with regional and global markets, Vietnam urgently needs to develop and enact a Carbon Market Law – a specialized law with high legal effect – while also supplementing relevant provisions in the Civil Code, tax laws, accounting laws, contract laws, and litigation laws. This is not only a requirement for international integration but also a prerequisite for Vietnam to maximize the potential of its abundant carbon credits, transforming climate commitments into opportunities for sustainable economic development in the new era of the nation.

Law on Carbon Credit Trading on the Voluntary Carbon Market

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